

**ORBITAL STATE ESTIMATION BASED ON THE EXTENDED KALMAN
FILTER WITH EMERGENCY SCENARIO**

By Dominik Frej

DEN318 Third Year Project (Aero) April 2023

Supervisors: Dr Tomasz Barciński, Dr Angadh Nanjangud

SCHOOL OF ENGINEERING AND MATERIALS SCIENCE
ENGINEERING/MATERIALS
THIRD YEAR PROJECT
DEN318/ MAT500

APRIL 2023

DECLARATION

This report entitled

**ORBITAL STATE ESTIMATION BASED ON THE EXTENDED KALMAN
FILTER WITH EMERGENCY SCENARIO**

Was composed by me and is based on my own work. Where the work of the others has been used, it is fully acknowledged in the text and in captions to table illustrations. This report has not been submitted for any other qualification.

Name: *Dominik Frej*

Signed:

Date: *25. 04. 2023*

Abstract

The Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) based on both central body (CG) and J2 perturbation (J2) gravity models were implemented to estimate the orbital state of a satellite in orbit around Earth. The estimate was compared to the trajectory generated by General Mission Analytical Tool (GMAT) which was assumed to be a real state. The onboard measurement was provided by the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) receiver. The EKF performance was verified by considering unfiltered measurement signals; it was found that the EKF reduces measurement error by up to 90%. To simulate an emergency scenario, the measured state was temporarily disengaged, and the capability of EKF to maintain low state estimation error was investigated. The simulation results proved that the state estimation of CG and J2 models are comparable if the satellite has continued access to measured data. The emergency study, however, found that the J2 model produces more accurate results by at least one order of magnitude as compared to the CG model. To investigate how quickly the true state can be restored after the emergency, the recovery time was examined and found to be on the order of 10 – 20 s for all cases studied.

Contents

List of Figures	v
List of Tables	vii
Chapter 1. Introduction	1
Chapter 2. Literature review	3
Chapter 3. Aims and objectives	7
3.1 Aims	7
3.2 Objectives	8
Chapter 4. Physics of orbital motion	9
4.1 Newton's Second Law of Motion	9
4.2 Gravitational field	9
4.3 Gravity models	10
Chapter 5. Extended Kalman filter	13
5.1 State-space model of satellite orbital motion	13
5.2 Discretization	18
5.3 State estimation with Extended Kalman filter	20
Chapter 6. Simulation results	23
6.1 Simulation setup	23
6.2 Orbital state estimation with random initial conditions	24
6.3 Orbital state estimation error with no measurement device failure	27
6.4 Orbital state estimation error with a measurement device failure	29

6.5 Orbital state estimation recovery from a measurement device failure	30
Chapter 7. Conclusions and future work	33
7.1 Conclusions	33
7.2 Future work	33
Chapter 8. Acknowledgements	35
Bibliography	37
Appendix A. Appendix A: Remaining figures	40
A.1 Orbital position of the satellite	40
A.2 Position coordinates of the satellite	42
A.3 Velocity coordinates of the satellite	43
Appendix B. Appendix B: Simulink model	45
B.1 Central gravity model diagram	45
B.2 Central gravity model function	46
B.3 J2 perturbation model diagram	49
B.4 J2 perturbation model function	49
Appendix C. Appendix C: MATLAB code	54
C.1 Central gravity model with no failure	54
C.2 Central gravity model with failure	59
C.3 J2 perturbation model with no failure	66
C.4 J2 perturbation model with failure	72

List of Figures

6.1 Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: J2 model, failure lasting 3000 s.	25
6.2 Time evolution of satellite of position: J2, 3000 s failure.	26
6.3 Magnified time evolution of satellite position: J2, 3000 s failure.	26
6.4 Time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, 3000 s failure.	26
6.5 Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, 3000 s failure.	26
6.6 Time evolution of satellite position error: no Kalman filter, no failure.	27
6.7 Time evolution of satellite velocity error: no Kalman filter, no failure.	27
6.8 Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, no failure.	28
6.9 Time evolution of satellite position error: J2, no failure.	28
6.10 Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, no failure.	28
6.11 Time evolution of satellite velocity error: J2 model, no failure.	28
6.12 Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, 3000 s failure.	29
6.13 Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, 3000 s failure.	29
6.14 Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, 3000 s failure.	30
6.15 Time evolution of satellite position error: J2, 3000 s failure.	30
6.16 Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, recovery after 3000 s failure.	31
6.17 Time evolution of satellite position error: J2, recovery after 3000 s failure.	31
6.18 Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, recovery after 3000 s failure.	31
6.19 Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, recovery after 3000 s failure.	31
A.1 Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: CG, no failure	40

A.2	Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: CG, 3000 s failure.	41
A.3	Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: J2, no failure.	41
A.4	Time evolution of satellite position: CG, no failure.	42
A.5	Magnified time evolution of satellite position: CG, no failure.	42
A.6	Time evolution of satellite position: CG, 3000 s failure.	42
A.7	Magnified time evolution of satellite position: CG, 3000 s failure.	42
A.8	Time evolution of satellite position: J2, 3000 s failure.	43
A.9	Magnified time evolution of satellite position: J2, 3000 s failure.	43
A.10	Time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, no failure.	43
A.11	Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, no failure.	43
A.12	Time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, 3000 s failure.	44
A.13	Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, 3000 s failure.	44
A.14	Time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, no failure.	44
A.15	Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, no failure.	44
B.1	Main body of central gravity model Simulink block diagram	45
B.2	Real satellite position and velocity (GMAT) block diagram.	46
B.3	Measurement device failure block diagram.	46
B.4	Main body of J2 perturbation model Simulink block diagram.	49
B.5	Real satellite position and velocity (GMAT) block diagram.	49
B.6	Measurement device failure block diagram.	49

List of Tables

6.1 Position estimation error summary.	32
6.2 Velocity estimation error summary.	32

Chapter 1

Introduction

Orbital state estimation is a crucial aspect of space mission planning and execution. It is essential to have precise knowledge about the position and velocity of satellite for various applications, such as orbit maintenance, formation flying, rendezvous, and interplanetary missions.

One of the most commonly used methods for orbital state estimation is filtering with the use of a dynamical system. This can be performed with Kalman filter which is a discrete time procedure for optimal estimating the state of the system. The extended Kalman filter (EKF) is an extension of the traditional Kalman filter, which is a recursive algorithm used for the optimal estimation of a linear dynamic system. The EKF can handle nonlinearities in the system by propagating the state using a nonlinear equation and approximating the covariance propagation with a linearized model. It has been widely applied in spacecraft orbit determination due to its robustness and computational efficiency.

In addition to the EKF, accurate modeling of the gravitational forces acting on a spacecraft is essential for precise orbital state estimation. In the central gravity (CG) model the only gravitational force acting on a space object is the force of a single massive body, typically a planet or a moon. However, for spacecraft in low Earth orbit (LEO), other perturbations must be considered, such as the J2 perturbation (J2) model. The J2 model accounts for the oblate shape of Earth and the resulting gravitational effects.

This thesis focuses on the development of an EKF-based algorithm for orbital state estimation using central gravity model or J2 model. The algorithm is applied in both standard and emergency cases to demonstrate its effectiveness in achieving accurate and reliable estimation of the spacecraft state.

Chapter 2

Literature review

Rudolf E. Kalman introduced the Kalman filter as numerical technique used to approximate the state of a system with noise signal.^[1] By utilizing the most recent measurement and the prior estimation, the filter is capable of iteratively revising its approximation of the system state, which is performed with an algorithm that considers the uncertainty of an object and the measurement. By reducing the average squared discrepancy between the approximated state and state of the system, it was proven that proposed approach is optimal and computationally efficient. The method, however, was limited to linearity and Gaussian distribution. Therefore, numerous extensions of traditional Kalman filters were developed, including EKF, unscented Kalman Filter (UKF), or particle Kalman filter (PKF).

Busse et al.^[2] elaborated on a robust orbital state estimation for a satellite fleet based on the EKF, linear Keplerian propagator, and carrier-phase Global Positioning System (GPS) sensor. The proposed approach handled random environmental disturbance with a maximum likelihood estimation algorithm; it achieved precision of 0.02 m and 0.0005 m/s in the estimation of relative state. A new approach to the time update phase of the EKF was presented by Mazzoni.^[3] A corrected Gauss-Legendre and Taylor-Heun methods were applied to estimate the nonlinear vector field and ensure positive semidefinite solutions; an adjustable step size was used to guarantee high precision at a low computational cost. Lee and Bang^[4] implemented EKF and UKF to estimate the positiona and velocity of two satellites, assuming

both CG and J2 models. Their study found that both filters perform well if the error of initial guess is moderate; otherwise, EKF failed to converge because of the linearization-related simplifications in the measurement phase, while UKF preserved low estimation error. Sanusi and Suparta⁵ combined the orbit estimator and orbit propagator to formulate an adjustable orbit determination algorithm. The proposed method was based on the EKF and Variation of Parameters to handle propagation between different states. The simulation results proved that the EKF can achieve great convergence rate and approximate the state of the satellite even without J2 approximation. Purivigraipong⁶ presented a straightforward orbit determination approach for LEO that used GPS data. The perturbations in the model were represented by the fourth term of zonal harmonics whereas the non-linear dynamics were handled with the EKF; the Simplified General Perturbations 4 (SGP4) model was used to generate the satellite orbit and the Simplified Deep Perturbations 4 was applied to propagate orbit of the GPS constellation. The error in velocity and position was found to be 2 m/s and 20 m respectively. Soken and Hajiyev⁷ increased the robustness of the EKF and UKF algorithms to address an abrupt malfunction in measurement. The proposed approach used a scale factor scheme to adjust the Kalman gain matrix and isolate flawed data but conserve other substantial information. As shown in the simulation, standard EKF and UKF required a relatively long time to recover back to the true state; for instance, UKF needed 700 s to re-converge after applying flaw for 50 seconds. In contrast, EKF and UKF disregarded flawed measurements and continuously provided expected estimations. This method can be especially useful when required attitude estimation accuracy is high, but measurements are limited.

Lee and Ricker⁸ presented a novel approach to control nonlinear systems using the EKF and Nonlinear Model Predictive Control techniques. A control law was formulated as an iterative algorithm to solve a problem of nonlinear optimization. Having employed EKF to approximate current state of the system, the authors could forecast its future behaviour. Lee and Ricker then used the NMPC algorithm to optimise objective function over a finite time

horizon. The proposed method proved to be robust and effective, yet it heavily depended on the precision of the estimation of the state and selected control input. Jing et al.^[9] introduced a method that uses Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) data for increasing classical orbit propagators precision that often involve errors due to modeling inaccuracies, unmodeled forces, and measurement errors. Gangal^[10] presented an orbit determination approach which included J2, J3, J4 zonal perturbations in combination with EKF; the reference state was provided by the onboard GNSS receiver. Gangal found that while J3 and J4 better represent trajectory deflections and have an impact on long-term integration, it was the J2 model that affected the state vector the most, and its exclusive use may reduce computational cost. A real-time orbital state determination with enhanced accuracy was developed by Saleem.^[11] The presented approach combined a dual-frequency GNSS receiver with an improved EKF that used an ionosphere-free code carrier phase (often applied for Precise Point Positioning^[12]) as a source of measurement. Roh et al.^[13] provided the UKF with the Magnetic Field Satellite data to obtain an orbital position estimation with an accuracy of 2 km. To validate the use of UKF, the simulation was also run with EKF. The demonstrated that the UKF can ensure much better accuracy than EKF for sampling intervals ≥ 20 s.

Karlgaard^[14] combined Least Squares (LS) and least absolute value methods to create a novel technique of state estimation for satellite rendezvous, the Huber estimator. The solution considered non-Gaussian random measurement errors, surpassing the accuracy of standard Kalman filters in return for a slight increase in computational cost. Liu et al.^[15] presented a novel approach for spacecraft state approximation defined as Maximum Correntropy Unscented Kalman Filter (MCUKF). This method used a maximum correntropy criterion instead of the traditional mean squared error. The authors explained that the correntropy criterion can be a more robust and reliable measure of similarity between two probability density functions, which makes it well-suited for applications with non-Gaussian noise and outliers. Liu et al. proved that the MCUKF approach has better performance than EKF and UKF with regards to accuracy and robustness, especially in scenarios with

high levels of measurement noise and outliers. A Bootstrap Particle Filter (PF) is proposed by Ramanathan and Chipade to estimate the state of satellite fleet.^[16] Having propagated particles close to the mean of the initial state, PF handles the inaccuracies due to the non-Gaussian measurement errors and non-linear dynamics. The simulation results show that PF is a much more accurate algorithm than LS, EKF, and UKF achieving an estimation accuracy of 1 m.

Mashiku et al.^[17] incorporate non-Gaussian uncertainties based on a non-linear Bayesian Particle Filter (BPF) that uses the Monte Carlo method to approximate a probability density function (PDF) for the orbit of high eccentricity. The BPF mean estimation error is lower by one order of magnitude as compared with EKF, while the PDF tends to be much more accurate as compared with Splitting Gaussian Mixture and does not require an additional filter to update measurements. Although this work assumed an idealized point-mass gravitational system with process noise as the only source of perturbations, it offers an accurate estimation of low probability yet significant potential orbital occurrences due to the full PDF representation. Li et al.^[18] propose a Cubature Kalman Filter (CKF) algorithm that used radar. The method integrates the advantages of CKF and spherical-radial rule, which can effectively improve the estimation accuracy while preserving relative simplicity of the system. Lastly, Kim et al.^[19] introduce the High Precision Orbit Propagator (HPOP) technique to enhance the fidelity of onboard orbit approximation systems. It was proven that HPOP technique increases precision of onboard OD systems by up to 60%, compared to the EKF and the SGP4 propagator.

Chapter 3

Aims and objectives

3.1 Aims

The main aims of the state estimation for satellite in Earth orbit based on the EKF are summarised in the form of research questions:

- (1) How accurate is the orbital state estimation based on the central gravity model in comparison to the J2 perturbations model?
 - (a) What is the state estimation error for the CG model?
 - (b) What is the state estimation error for the J2 model?
- (2) How does the accuracy of the orbital state estimation change in the case of measurement device failure?
 - (a) How does the sudden failure in state measurements affect the estimated orbital position of the satellite based on the CG model?
 - (b) How does the sudden failure in state measurements affect the estimated orbital position of the satellite based on the J2 model?
- (3) How quickly is the EKF able to recover from temporary measurement device failure?
 - (a) How much time is needed for the CG model to converge back to the true orbital state?
 - (b) How much time is needed for the J2 model to converge back to the true orbital state?

3.2 Objectives

The EKF-based algorithm coupled with the fourth-order Runge Kutta (RK4) integration approach and CG and J2 models is proposed in this work to obtain the state estimation for the satellite in orbit around Earth. The reference orbital state is generated in the General Mission Analysis Tool (GMAT), simulating the real orbital motion of the satellite. The use of GMAT instead of actual orbital data is motivated by the lack of access to open-source satellite databases and GMAT's high accuracy.²⁰ The use of EKF is validated by analysing convergence from an initial guess and for filtered and unfiltered measurement signals. To simulate an emergency, the measuring device is temporarily switched off; the comparative analysis of state estimation error and recovery time is conducted. The models of the system are created in Simulink and simulations are run in MATLAB on MacBook Pro with M1 processor and 16 GB RAM.

Chapter 4

Physics of orbital motion

4.1 Newton's Second Law of Motion

In his opus magnum, Newton proved that an object acceleration is inversely proportional to its mass and directly proportional to force acting on it. The motion of the satellite in orbit around Earth can be described with (4.1) as it can be assumed that the only significant force acting on such satellite is the gravitational force of the Earth.^[21]

$$\mathbf{F}_g = m\mathbf{a} \quad (4.1)$$

where \mathbf{F}_g is the gravity force acting on the satellite, m is the scalar mass of the satellite, and \mathbf{a} is the satellite acceleration vector originating in the point-mass.

4.2 Gravitational field

According to the Universal Law of Gravitation, the gravity field generated by the point-mass M can be represented by:^[21]

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}(\mathbf{r}) = -G \frac{M}{|\mathbf{r}|^2} \frac{\mathbf{r}}{|\mathbf{r}|} \quad (4.2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\gamma}$ is the gravitational field vector, G is the gravitational constant, M is the mass of the body generating the field, and \mathbf{r} is the position vector. On the other hand, the gravitational

field for a continuous body is:

$$\boldsymbol{\gamma}(\mathbf{r}) = -G \iiint \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}')(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}')}{|\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'|^3} dV' \quad (4.3)$$

where $\rho(\mathbf{r}')$ is the mass density at position \mathbf{r}' , and \mathbf{r} and \mathbf{r}' are position vectors. Therefore, the force acting on the body of mass m is expressed by:

$$\mathbf{F}_g(\mathbf{r}) = \boldsymbol{\gamma}(\mathbf{r})m \quad (4.4)$$

where $\mathbf{F}_g(\mathbf{r})$ represents the gravitational force at position \mathbf{r} due to the gravitational attraction of all the mass elements in the region of interest, V' is the volume of integration that contains the mass elements.

The equations (4.1) and (4.2) form differential equation of the satellite movement which is independent of the satellite mass:

$$m\mathbf{a} = \boldsymbol{\gamma}(\mathbf{r})m \quad (4.5)$$

therefore

$$\mathbf{a} = \boldsymbol{\gamma}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (4.6)$$

In Cartesian coordinates $\mathbf{a} = \ddot{\mathbf{r}}$, then

$$\ddot{\mathbf{r}} = \boldsymbol{\gamma}(\mathbf{r}) \quad (4.7)$$

The dynamics of orbital motion can be expressed with (4.7) in which the acceleration of the satellite is the function of position and gravitational field only.²¹

4.3 Gravity models

4.3.1 Central gravity model

The central gravity model is a simplified orbital dynamics model which characterizes the movement of a satellite in the vicinity of a single celestial body. In this analysis, Earth is

treated as a central body and the satellite as a point mass in orbit around the Earth. The assumptions of the model are the following:^[21]

- central body and its gravitational field have an ideally spherical shape,
- central body is fixed at the origin of a three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system,
- satellite is influenced solely by the central body gravitational force,
- any perturbations or external forces are not existent.

The gravitation field for the central-body model can be represented by (4.2).^[21]

4.3.2 J2 perturbation model

The J2 second zonal harmonic perturbation model is a mathematical model used to express Earth oblateness. The model assumes that the Earth is an ellipsoid, meaning it does not have a perfectly spherical shape and its equatorial radius is larger than its polar radius.^[22] The assumptions of the model are the following:

- Earth is an oblate spheroid, and its gravity field can be modelled as a sum of spherical harmonics,
- only non-spherical term considered is the J2 term, which represents Earth oblateness,
- orbit is circular and coplanar with Earth equator,
- perturbations of Sun, Moon, and other planets are neglected,

The gravitational field for the J2 model is:^[23]

$$\gamma_x(\mathbf{r}) = -GM \frac{r_x}{r^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{r_z^2}{r^4} \right) \quad (4.8)$$

$$\gamma_y(\mathbf{r}) = -GM \frac{r_y}{r^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{r_z^2}{r^4} \right) \quad (4.9)$$

$$\gamma_z(\mathbf{r}) = -GM \frac{r_z}{r^3} \left(1 + \frac{9}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{r_z^2}{r^4} \right) \quad (4.10)$$

\mathbf{r} is position vector with Cartesian coordinates r_x, r_y, r_z , r is distance between the center of Earth and satellite, R_e is the equatorial radius, and J_2 is Earth spherical harmonic equal to 0.001082.^[22]

Chapter 5

Extended Kalman filter

5.1 State-space model of satellite orbital motion

5.1.1 State-space model

A state-space characterizes dynamic system behaviour; it involves time evolution and measurement components. While former expresses change of state variables, the later couples the system output variables with state variables. The state equations are described by: [2425](#)

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x}_1(t) &= f_1(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t)) \\ \dot{x}_2(t) &= f_2(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t)) \\ &\vdots \\ \dot{x}_n(t) &= f_n(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t))\end{aligned}\tag{5.1}$$

$$\begin{aligned}y_1(t) &= g_1(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t)) \\ y_2(t) &= g_2(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t)) \\ &\vdots \\ y_m(t) &= g_m(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t))\end{aligned}\tag{5.2}$$

where $x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t)$ are state variables, $w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t)$ are model disturbance, $y_1(t), y_2(t), \dots, y_m(t)$ are the output variables, $v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t)$ are the measurement noise,

$f_1(\cdot), f_2(\cdot), \dots, f_n(\cdot)$ and $g_1(\cdot), g_2(\cdot), \dots, g_m(\cdot)$ are vector fields. Defining following vectors 2524

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1(t) \\ x_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ x_n(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.3)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} y_1(t) \\ y_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ y_m(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.4)$$

$$\mathbf{w}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} w_1(t) \\ w_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ w_r(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.5)$$

$$\mathbf{v}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} v_1(t) \\ v_2(t) \\ \vdots \\ v_l(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.6)$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{w}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} f_1(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t)) \\ f_2(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t)) \\ \vdots \\ f_n(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); w_1(t), w_2(t), \dots, w_r(t)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.7)$$

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{v}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} g_1(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t)) \\ g_2(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t)) \\ \vdots \\ g_n(x_1(t), x_2(t), \dots, x_n(t); v_1(t), v_2(t), \dots, v_l(t)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.8)$$

thus the equations can be written in compact form

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{w}(t)) \quad (5.9)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{v}(t)) \quad (5.10)$$

If the functions \mathbf{f} and \mathbf{g} are linear with respect to \mathbf{x} , \mathbf{w} , and \mathbf{v} , i.e.

$$f(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w}) = A\mathbf{x} + B\mathbf{w} \quad (5.11)$$

$$g(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) = C\mathbf{x} + D\mathbf{v} \quad (5.12)$$

then

$$\dot{x} = Ax + Bu \quad (5.13)$$

$$y = Cx + Du \quad (5.14)$$

where matrices A, B, C, and D characterise dynamics and the measurements of the system.

5.1.2 State-space model for central gravity

The Cartesian coordinate system is often used for state space models because it provides a convenient way to represent the variables and dynamics of the system that change over time.

Therefore, the gravitational field in Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z) can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_x &= -\frac{GM}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x \\ \gamma_y &= -\frac{GM}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}y \\ \gamma_z &= -\frac{GM}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}z \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

On the other hand, the orbital motion of the satellite can be represented by:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{x} &= -\frac{GM}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x \\ \ddot{y} &= -\frac{GM}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}y \\ \ddot{z} &= -\frac{GM}{(x^2+y^2+z^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}z \end{aligned} \quad (5.16)$$

Before the final state-space set of equations for the CG model can be derived, the state variables must be introduced:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_1 &:= x \\
x_2 &:= y \\
x_3 &:= z \\
x_4 &:= v_x = \dot{x} \\
x_5 &:= v_y = \dot{y} \\
x_6 &:= v_z = \dot{z}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.17}$$

where x , y , z , v_x , v_y , v_z are satellite position and velocity components that can also be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{x}_1 &= x_4 \\
\dot{x}_2 &= x_5 \\
\dot{x}_3 &= x_6 \\
\dot{x}_4 &= -\frac{GM}{(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x_1 \\
\dot{x}_5 &= -\frac{GM}{(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x_2 \\
\dot{x}_6 &= -\frac{GM}{(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x_3
\end{aligned} \tag{5.18}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \\ \dot{x}_3 \\ \dot{x}_4 \\ \dot{x}_5 \\ \dot{x}_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_4 + w_1 \\ x_5 + w_2 \\ x_6 + w_3 \\ -\frac{GM}{(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x_1 + w_4 \\ -\frac{GM}{(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x_2 + w_5 \\ -\frac{GM}{(x_1^2+x_2^2+x_3^2)^{\frac{3}{2}}}x_3 + w_6 \end{bmatrix} =: \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \tag{5.19}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ y_4 \\ y_5 \\ y_6 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 + v_1 \\ x_2 + v_2 \\ x_3 + v_3 \\ x_4 + v_4 \\ x_5 + v_5 \\ x_6 + v_6 \end{bmatrix} := \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) \quad (5.20)$$

where $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ is the state function, $\mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x})$ is the measurement function, \mathbf{v} is the measurement noise, and \mathbf{w} is the model and discretization disturbance.

5.1.3 State-space for J2 perturbation model

In Cartesian coordinates the gravitational field is expressed by:

$$\gamma_x(\mathbf{r}) = -GM \frac{r_x}{r^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{r_z^2}{r^4} \right) \quad (5.21)$$

$$\gamma_y(\mathbf{r}) = -GM \frac{r_y}{r^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{r_z^2}{r^4} \right) \quad (5.22)$$

$$\gamma_z(\mathbf{r}) = -GM \frac{r_z}{r^3} \left(1 + \frac{9}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{r_z^2}{r^4} \right) \quad (5.23)$$

$$r^2 = r_x^2 + r_y^2 + r_z^2 \quad (5.24)$$

whereas equations describing the orbital motion of the satellite are:

$$\ddot{x} = -GM \frac{x}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{z^2}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^4} \right) \quad (5.25)$$

$$\ddot{y} = -GM \frac{y}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{z^2}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^4} \right) \quad (5.26)$$

$$\ddot{z} = -GM \frac{z}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^3} \left(1 + \frac{9}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{z^2}{(x^2 + y^2 + z^2)^4} \right) \quad (5.27)$$

Before the final state-space set of equations for the central gravity model can be derived, the state variables must be introduced:

$$\begin{aligned}
x_1 &:= x \\
x_2 &:= y \\
x_3 &:= z \\
x_4 &:= v_x = \dot{x} \\
x_5 &:= v_y = \dot{y} \\
x_6 &:= v_z = \dot{z}
\end{aligned} \tag{5.28}$$

where x , y , z and v_x , v_y , v_z are satellite position and velocity components which can also be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
\dot{x}_1 &= x_4 \\
\dot{x}_2 &= x_5 \\
\dot{x}_3 &= x_6 \\
\dot{x}_4 &= -GM \frac{x}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{z^2}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^4} \right) x_1 \\
\dot{x}_5 &= -GM \frac{x}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{z^2}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^4} \right) x_2 \\
\dot{x}_6 &= -GM \frac{x}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^3} \left(1 + \frac{3}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{1}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^2} - \frac{15}{2} J_2 R_e^2 \frac{z^2}{(x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2)^4} \right) x_3
\end{aligned} \tag{5.29}$$

These equations can be integrated numerically to compute the state of the satellite at any time given the initial conditions.

5.2 Discretization

5.2.1 Continuous and discrete time

In continuous-time systems, the input, output, and state variables vary continuously with respect to time, while discrete-time systems sample these quantities at discrete time intervals.

The continuous-time state-space system can be expressed by:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \quad (5.30)$$

can be reintroduced as discrete-time $k \in N$, which is related to the continuous time by:

$$t = T_s k \quad (5.31)$$

where T_s is sampling time and k is discrete time while the discrete-time system is:

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = \mathbf{f}_d(\mathbf{x}(k)) \quad (5.32)$$

where \mathbf{f}_d is vector field.

5.2.2 State-space model discretization with fourth-order Runge-Kutta method

To run simulations, state-space model must be transformed from continuous time into discrete-time domain. One common solution is the RK4 technique that approximates state vector at next time interval. [2627](#)

$$\mathbf{x}(k+1) = \mathbf{x}(k) + \frac{T_s}{6}(\mathbf{K}_1 + 2\mathbf{K}_2 + 2\mathbf{K}_3 + \mathbf{K}_4) \quad (5.33)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{K}_1 &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(k)) \\ \mathbf{K}_2 &= \mathbf{f}\left(\mathbf{x}(k) + T_s \frac{\mathbf{K}_1}{2}\right) \\ \mathbf{K}_3 &= \mathbf{f}\left(\mathbf{x}(k) + T_s \frac{\mathbf{K}_2}{2}\right) \\ \mathbf{K}_4 &= \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(k) + T_s \mathbf{K}_3) \end{aligned} \quad (5.34)$$

where \mathbf{K}_1 , \mathbf{K}_2 , \mathbf{K}_3 , \mathbf{K}_4 are RK4 parameters vectors. This discretization method is applicable to both CG and J2 models.

5.3 State estimation with Extended Kalman filter

The EKF predicts the future state of the system by utilizing information about its current state and then refines the prediction with newly acquired measurements. The prediction step applies a nonlinear function to the previous state estimate, while the update step computes the disproportion between the predicted and actual measurements, and combines predicted state estimate with measurement information to update the state estimate. This updated estimate is a weighted average of the predicted and measured state, accounting for the uncertainty in each.

Before employing the Kalman filter, equations describing system and measurements must be considered.²⁴

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(k-1), \mathbf{w}(k-1)) \quad (5.35)$$

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}(k), \mathbf{v}(k)) \quad (5.36)$$

$$\mathbf{w}(k) \sim N(0, \mathbf{Q}(k)) \quad (5.37)$$

$$\mathbf{v}(k) \sim N(0, \mathbf{R}(k)) \quad (5.38)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k)$ describes the current system state, $\mathbf{w}(k-1)$ is model disturbance, $\mathbf{y}(k)$ represents a measurement, $\mathbf{v}(k)$ is the measurement noise containing modelling inaccuracies (e.g., due to RK4 method), $N(0, \mathbf{Q}(k))$ and $N(0, \mathbf{R}(k))$ mean normal distribution with mean equal to 0 and covariance equal to \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} respectively. The algorithm executes following steps:²⁴

(1) Initialization phase

Kalman filtering starts with an initial guess represented by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^+(0) = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}(0)) \quad (5.39)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^+(0) = \mathbf{E}[(\mathbf{x}(0) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}^+)(\mathbf{x}(0) - \hat{\mathbf{x}}^+)^T] \quad (5.40)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{x}}^+$ is the state estimation of the expected value a posteriori considering the state of the measurement, \mathbf{E} represents the expected value of the state, \mathbf{P}^+ is the

state covariance, and \mathbf{x} is the state of the system.

(2) Linearization phase

For the subsequent time instants $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$ the partial derivatives of \mathbf{f} must be calculated:

$$\mathbf{F}(k-1) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}=\hat{\mathbf{x}}^+(k-1)} \quad (5.41)$$

$$\mathbf{L}(k-1) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}=\hat{\mathbf{x}}^+(k-1)} \quad (5.42)$$

where \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{L} are linearization matrices.

(3) Propagation phase

To acquire a time update of both the state estimate and covariance estimation error, it is necessary to calculate following equations:

$$\mathbf{P}^-(k) = \mathbf{F}(k-1)\mathbf{P}^+(k-1)\mathbf{F}^T(k-1) + \mathbf{L}(k-1)\mathbf{Q}(k-1)\mathbf{L}^T(k-1) \quad (5.43)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(k) = \mathbf{f}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^+(k-1), 0) \quad (5.44)$$

where minus in superscript represents a priori in instance k and plus means a posteriori in instance $k-1$.

(4) Correction phase

To linearise the measurement equation, the following partial derivative matrices must be computed:

$$\mathbf{H}(k) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{w})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}=\hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(k)} \quad (5.45)$$

$$\mathbf{M}(k) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{h}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right|_{\mathbf{x}=\hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(k)} \quad (5.46)$$

where \mathbf{H} and \mathbf{M} are linearization matrices.

(5) Update phase

The update of the state estimation and covariance error can be executed by:

$$\mathbf{K}(k) = \mathbf{P}^-(k)\mathbf{H}^T(k)(\mathbf{H}(k)\mathbf{P}^-(k)\mathbf{H}^T(k) + \mathbf{M}(k)\mathbf{R}(k)\mathbf{M}^T(k))^{-1} \quad (5.47)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k) = \hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(k) + \mathbf{K}(k)[\mathbf{y}(k) - \mathbf{h}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}^-(k), 0)] \quad (5.48)$$

$$\mathbf{P}^+(k) = (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{K}(k)\mathbf{H}(k))\mathbf{P}^-(k) \quad (5.49)$$

The eEKF for both CG and J2 models can be implemented by using (5.19) and (5.20) and executing the steps above.

Chapter 6

Simulation results

6.1 Simulation setup

6.1.1 General Mission Analysis Tool

The orbital motion of the satellite referred to as real was generated in the open-source GMAT. It was assumed that the satellite is equipped in the GNSS receiver of Gaussian measurement error with $3\sigma = 100$ m in position and $3\sigma = 2$ m/s in velocity measurements. The orbit generated in GMAT was based on the Joint Gravity Model of the fourth degree and order, the Mass Spectrometer Incoherent Scatter Extended-1990 atmospheric model, and the spherical drag model with Earth fixed in the origin of the three-dimensional Cartesian coordinates system. The initial conditions of the generated orbital motion are following:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -598.8291258411485 \\ 7.616498417452651 \\ 6844.851117871764 \\ -0.0007318034561573418 \\ 7.616495283684098 \\ -0.008387905564010312 \end{bmatrix} \quad (6.1)$$

where x, y, z are position coordinates in m and v_x, v_y, v_z are velocity coordinates in m/s. The complete orbital motion data was generated in GMAT with a frequency of 1 Hz, typical for control systems of small satellites.²⁸

6.1.2 Simulink MATLAB

Simulink MATLAB was used to create two separate block diagrams for state estimation based on the CG and J2 models. The Simulink models were combined with data from GMAT to generate a comparison between real and estimated orbital states.

6.2 Orbital state estimation with random initial conditions

Figure 6.1 portrays the trajectory of the satellite orbit generated in GMAT (blue) and estimated with EKF (red). To validate capabilities of the EKF, the estimated orbital position was based on the following random initial guess:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ v_x \\ v_y \\ v_z \end{bmatrix}^T = - \begin{bmatrix} 10000000 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 6000 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (6.2)$$

where x, y, z are position coordinates in m and v_x, v_y, v_z are velocity coordinates in m/s. This was to simulate a scenario in which the satellite is lost and EKF must recover its supposed trajectory.

As can be seen in 6.1, the estimated orbital position successfully converges to the real orbital state. However, the curves do not overlap each other for a part of the satellite

FIGURE 6.1. Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: J2 model, failure lasting 3000 s.

orbit. This break is expected and represents a temporary failure of the measurement device discussed in detail in [6.4](#)

The implemented EKF provides a stable position estimation as shown in [6.2](#). The convergence from the initial guess is equal to 350 s, as seen in [6.3](#), which constitutes around 5% of the 6000 s orbit and thus is within the acceptable limit. Moreover, the estimation process for the satellite’s velocity is stable. The initial estimation deviations (v_x est. and v_z est.) peaks in 0 – 50 s are the result of the filter characteristics which favors short convergence time and may cause occasional overshoots. The initial condition for v_y est. happened to be relatively close to v_y real, thus its convergence time is much shorter as compared to v_x est. and v_z est. The total convergence time is also equal to 350 s.

FIGURE 6.2. Time evolution of satellite of position: J2, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.3. Magnified time evolution of satellite position: J2, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.4. Time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.5. Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, 3000 s failure.

The results for the other three considered simulation cases are available in Appendix [A](#) since they present highly comparable results to those in [6.2](#), [6.3](#), [6.4](#), [6.5](#).

6.3 Orbital state estimation error with no measurement device failure

For the sake of clear visual representation, figures in sections [6.3](#) and [6.4](#) present results over the second half of the orbit, i.e., between 3000 s and 6000 s.

FIGURE 6.6. Time evolution of satellite position error: no Kalman filter, no failure.

FIGURE 6.7. Time evolution of satellite velocity error: no Kalman filter, no failure.

The advantage of using EKF can be seen while comparing [6.6](#) and [6.7](#) with [6.8](#), [6.9](#), [6.10](#), and [6.11](#). The data received from the onboard orbital state measurement device is subject to measurement Gaussian error where $3\sigma = 100$ m in position measurement and $3\sigma = 2$ m/s in velocity measurement as seen in [6.6](#) and [6.7](#). The noise, however, can be filtered out by EKF which reduces measurement error by 90% for position estimation and 70% for velocity estimation; a new normal distribution of the measurement error is $3\sigma = 10$ m in position measurements and $3\sigma = 0.6$ m/s in velocity measurements as presented in [6.8](#), [6.9](#), [6.10](#), and [6.11](#).

FIGURE 6.8. Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, no failure.

FIGURE 6.9. Time evolution of satellite position error: J2, no failure.

FIGURE 6.10. Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, no failure.

FIGURE 6.11. Time evolution of satellite velocity error: J2 model, no failure.

There is no major difference in state estimation based on the CG model as compared to the J2 model if there is no measuring device failure [6.1](#) [6.2](#). This suggests that the CG model might be better choice for creating proof of concept or early-stage prototype than the J2 model because of the cost and simplicity. However, space missions are subject to high risk, thus they must account for emergencies by including redundancy in the system and contingency solutions. [2229](#)

6.4 Orbital state estimation error with a measurement device failure

The temporary failure of the measurement device is simulated for 2000 s which constitutes 33.33% of the assumed orbit. It is worth noting that once the failure is started in the 3500 s of the simulation, the estimation error is free from the measurement noise as expected, assuming there is no other source of measurement. Figure [6.12](#) shows that the position

FIGURE 6.12. Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.13. Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, 3000 s failure.

estimation error based on the CG model increases by two orders of magnitude, as compared to values in [6.8](#), with a range equal to 5591 m and $3\sigma = 4440$ m. On the other hand, the position estimation error based on the J2 model shown in [6.13](#) increases by one order of magnitude, as compared to the result in [6.9](#), with a range equal to 424.3 m and $3\sigma = 516.3$ m.

FIGURE 6.14. Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.15. Time evolution of satellite position error: J2, 3000 s failure.

For the velocity estimation based on the CG model presented in [6.14](#), the error increases by one order of magnitude as compared to the error in [6.10](#), with a range equal to 13.28 m/s and $3\sigma = 9.801$ m. The equivalent error based on the J2 model seen in [6.15](#) achieves a range of 1.543 m/s and $3\sigma = 0.6081$ m/s, which is comparable to the values obtained if no measurement failure occurs presented in [6.11](#). While looking at [6.12](#), [6.13](#), [6.14](#), [6.15](#), it can be clearly seen that the J2 model outperforms the CG model, generating lower estimation error in position and velocity by at least one order of magnitude in case of emergency as summarised in [6.1](#) and [6.2](#). It is worth noting, however, that in the case of measurement device failure, 3σ does not fully reflect the performance of the system due to the lack of randomness provided by the measurement noise otherwise. Thus, Monte Carlo method with randomized initial guess should be considered in the future investigation.

6.5 Orbital state estimation recovery from a measurement device failure

In [6.16](#), [6.17](#), [6.18](#), [6.19](#) it can be seen that EKF is able to recover satellite position and velocity within 10 – 20 s after the signal containing the satellite state measurement became

available again for both CG and J2 models. The recovery time of the order of seconds is acceptable as it represents around 0.05 % of 6000 s orbit.

FIGURE 6.16. Time evolution of satellite position error: CG, recovery after 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.17. Time evolution of satellite position error: J2, recovery after 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.18. Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, recovery after 3000 s failure.

FIGURE 6.19. Time evolution of satellite velocity error: CG, recovery after 3000 s failure.

The failure of the measuring device may also represent a rare access to the measurements that are characteristic of satellites without GNSS receiver that rely solely on Satellite Laser Ranging (SLR). In such a scenario, the laser-measured state is available to the satellite at

intervals (e.g., every hour³⁰), thus short recovery time plays a crucial role in accurate and safe satellite trajectory adjustments.

6.5.1 State estimation error summary

TABLE 6.1. Position estimation error summary.

Position estimation error	3σ [m]	Range [m]
Position estimation error: CG, no failure	14.028	27.4
Position estimation error: J2, no failure	13.479	27.49
Position estimation error: CG, failure	4440	5591
Position estimation error: J2, failure	516.3	424.3

TABLE 6.2. Velocity estimation error summary.

Velocity estimation error	3σ [m/s]	Range [m/s]
Velocity estimation error: CG, no failure	0.5187	1.299
Velocity estimation error: J2, no failure	0.57	1.346
Velocity estimation error: CG, failure	9.801	13.28
Velocity estimation error: J2, failure	0.6081	1.543

Chapter 7

Conclusions and future work

7.1 Conclusions

The investigation of the orbital state estimation with the use of EKF was completed successfully. The simulation was run for four cases, namely state estimation based on the CG and J2 models with and without measuring device failure. The results showed that the EKF can reduce state estimation error up to 90%. It was also shown that the CG and J2 models are of comparable accuracy in standard conditions. However, J2 offers a significant advantage in case of a temporary lack of measurements; its estimation error is smaller by at least one order of magnitude as compared to CG. Lastly, the recovery time of 10 – 20 s was identified for both models, which is within the acceptable limits. The results of this study underline the filtering capabilities of EKF and proved the robustness of the J2 model over the CG model.

7.2 Future work

The presented study can be further developed by implementing more advanced gravity models, such as SGP4 or Goddard Mars Model 3, that minimise estimation error over longer periods without measurements.⁶ This may be useful in scenarios where GNSS signal is

scarce or not available at all, including lunar and Martian orbits. The more complex gravity models may be coupled with a Field Programmable Gate Array system that ensures more computational power and lower estimation errors.^[31] Moreover, the actual discretized measurement error is not Gaussian, thus MCKF,^[15] Huber estimator,^[14] or BPF^[17] may be applied to increase the probability of avoiding unlikely accidents. On the other hand, variational integrators may be considered in exchange for RK4 to reduce computational costs while preserving high fidelity.^[32,33] Lastly, a Monte Carlo simulation can be run to further validate obtained results.^[17]

Chapter 8

Acknowledgements

This thesis is a product of hard work that lasted over last 4 weeks and friendship that started a year ago.

Dr Angadh Nanjangud, Queen Mary University of London

Dear Angu, Thank you for helping me out with PhD application and thesis and that you provided me with a lot of support, both academically and mentally.

Dr Tomasz Barciński, Space Research Center of the Polish Academy of Sciences

Dear Tomek, You are just incredible. I would like you to know that I do appreciate your time, energy, wisdom, and awesome humor. You have become my teacher, mentor, and friend above all. You are the best. Thank you.

Dear grandparents and grandparents,

You have taught me a lot and thank you for always taking care of me. I love y'all.

Dear Mum and Dad,

I would not be here today if it was not for you. Thank you with all my heart. I love you, you are the best parents in the world.

Dear my God and Gods of others,

It is cool to be an engineer and capable of love human being. Thanks for that.

Dominik :)

Bibliography

- [1] R. E. Kalman, “A new approach to linear filtering and prediction problems,” 1960.
- [2] F. D. Busse, J. P. How, and J. Simpson, “Demonstration of adaptive extended kalman filter for low-earth-orbit formation estimation using cdgps,” *Navigation*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 79–93, 2003.
- [3] T. Mazzoni, “Computational aspects of continuous–discrete extended kalman-filtering,” *Computational Statistics*, vol. 23, pp. 519–539, 2008.
- [4] Y.-G. Lee and H. Bang, “Relative state estimation of satellite formation flying using kalman filter,” *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 2111–2116, 2008.
- [5] H. Sanusi and W. Suparta, “Open platform orbit determination systems using a mixture of orbit estimator and orbit propagator,” *Space Science and Communication for Sustainability*, pp. 223–238, 2018.
- [6] S. Purivigraipong and S. Kuntanapreeda, “Spacecraft orbit determination from code information of global positioning system signals,” in *TENCON 2005-2005 IEEE Region 10 Conference*. IEEE, 2005, pp. 1–6.
- [7] H. E. Soken, C. Hajiyev, and S.-i. Sakai, “Robust kalman filtering for small satellite attitude estimation in the presence of measurement faults,” *European Journal of Control*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 64–72, 2014.
- [8] J. H. Lee and N. L. Ricker, “Extended kalman filter based nonlinear model predictive control,” *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Research*, vol. 33, no. 6, pp. 1530–1541, 1994.
- [9] S. Jing, X. Zhan, and Z. Zhu, “Spacecraft orbit propagator integration with gnss in a simulated scenario,” *Advances in Space Research*, vol. 60, no. 5, pp. 1062–1079, 2017.
- [10] S. Gangal, “Development of on-board orbit determination system for low earth orbit (leo) satellite using global navigation satellite system (gnss) receiver,” in *Geospatial World Forum*, 2011.
- [11] Z. Saleem, “Extended kalman filter for optimal determination of position, velocity and time of earth orbiting satellites using carrier phase measurements from gnss constellations,” 2011.
- [12] P. Li and X. Zhang, “Integrating gps and glonass to accelerate convergence and initialization times of precise point positioning,” *GPS solutions*, vol. 18, pp. 461–471, 2014.

- [13] K.-M. Roh, S.-Y. Park, and K.-H. Choi, "Orbit determination using the geomagnetic field measurement via the unscented kalman filter," *Journal of Spacecraft and Rockets*, vol. 44, no. 1, pp. 246–253, 2007.
- [14] C. D. Karlgaard, "Robust rendezvous navigation in elliptical orbit," *Journal of guidance, control, and dynamics*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 495–499, 2006.
- [15] X. Liu, H. Qu, J. Zhao, P. Yue, and M. Wang, "Maximum correntropy unscented kalman filter for spacecraft relative state estimation," *Sensors*, vol. 16, no. 9, p. 1530, 2016.
- [16] T. Ramanathan and R. A. Chipade, "Comparative evaluation of statistical orbit determination algorithms for short-term prediction of geostationary and geosynchronous satellite orbits in navic constellation," *arXiv preprint arXiv:2111.12348*, 2021.
- [17] A. Mashiku, J. Garrison, and J. R. Carpenter, "Statistical orbit determination using the particle filter for incorporating non-gaussian uncertainties." in *AIAA/AAS Astrodynamics Specialist Conference*, 2012, p. 5063.
- [18] Z. Li, W. Yang, D. Ding, and Y. Liao, "A novel fifth-degree cubature kalman filter for real-time orbit determination by radar," *Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, vol. 2017, 2017.
- [19] E.-H. Kim, B.-H. Lee, S.-B. Park, H.-P. Jin, H.-W. Lee, and Y.-H. Jeong, "Performance improvement of real time on-board orbit determination using high precision orbit propagator," *Journal of the Korean Society for Aeronautical & Space Sciences*, vol. 44, no. 9, pp. 781–788, 2016.
- [20] S. P. Hughes, D. J. Conway, and J. Parker, "Using the general mission analysis tool (gmat)," in *AAS Guidance and Control Conference*, no. GSFC-E-DAA-TN39043, 2017.
- [21] H. Schaub and J. L. Junkins, *Analytical mechanics of space systems*. Aiaa, 2003.
- [22] J. R. Wertz, D. F. Everett, and J. J. Puschell, "Space mission engineering: the new smad," (*No Title*), 2011.
- [23] J. Marcel, "Sidi. spacecraft dynamics and control. ed. por robert f. stengel michael j. rycroft," 1997.
- [24] D. Simon, *Optimal state estimation: Kalman, H infinity, and nonlinear approaches*. John Wiley & Sons, 2006.
- [25] K. Ogata *et al.*, *Modern control engineering*. Prentice hall Upper Saddle River, NJ, 2010, vol. 5.
- [26] P. Frogerais, J.-J. Bellanger, and L. Senhadji, "Various ways to compute the continuous-discrete extended kalman filter," *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 1000–1004, 2011.
- [27] J. R. Dormand and P. J. Prince, "A family of embedded runge-kutta formulae," *Journal of computational and applied mathematics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 19–26, 1980.

- [28] N. Roussel, G. Ramillien, F. Frappart, J. Darrozes, A. Gay, R. Biancale, N. Striebig, V. Hanquiez, X. Bertin, and D. Allain, “Sea level monitoring and sea state estimate using a single geodetic receiver,” *Remote sensing of Environment*, vol. 171, pp. 261–277, 2015.
- [29] S. Dole, “Contingency planning for space-flight emergencies,” in *4th Annual Meeting and Technical Display*, 1967, p. 825.
- [30] S. Jung, S.-Y. Park, H.-E. Park, C.-D. Park, S.-W. Kim, and Y.-S. Jang, “Real-time determination of relative position between satellites using laser ranging,” *Journal of Astronomy and Space Sciences*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 351–362, 2012.
- [31] X. Jiang, J. Tao, and Z. Zhang, “Implementation of extended kalman filter on fpga,” 2011.
- [32] Y. Lishkova, S. Ober-Blöbaum, M. Cannon, and S. Leyendecker, “A multirate variational approach to simulation and optimal control for flexible spacecraft,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2009.05873*, 2020.
- [33] Y. Lishkova, M. Cannon, and S. Ober-Blöbaum, “A multirate variational approach to nonlinear mpc,” in *2022 European Control Conference (ECC)*. IEEE, 2022, pp. 729–735.

Chapter A

Appendix A: Remaining figures

A.1 Orbital position of the satellite

FIGURE A.1. Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: CG, no failure

FIGURE A.2. Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE A.3. Real and estimated orbital position of the satellite: J2, no failure.

A.2 Position coordinates of the satellite

FIGURE A.4. Time evolution of satellite position: CG, no failure.

FIGURE A.5. Magnified time evolution of satellite position: CG, no failure.

FIGURE A.6. Time evolution of satellite position: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE A.7. Magnified time evolution of satellite position: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE A.8. Time evolution of satellite position: J2, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE A.9. Magnified time evolution of satellite position: J2, 3000 s failure.

A.3 Velocity coordinates of the satellite

FIGURE A.10. Time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, no failure.

FIGURE A.11. Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, no failure.

FIGURE A.12. Time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE A.13. Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: CG, 3000 s failure.

FIGURE A.14. Time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, no failure.

FIGURE A.15. Magnified time evolution of satellite velocity: J2, no failure.

Chapter B

Appendix B: Simulink model

B.1 Central gravity model diagram

The files with Simulink diagrams are available upon request.

FIGURE B.1. Main body of central gravity model Simulink block diagram

FIGURE B.2. Real satellite position and velocity (GMAT) block diagram.

FIGURE B.3. Measurement device failure block diagram.

B.2 Central gravity model function

```
function [x_updated, P_updated] = orbit_kalman(x, P, x_meas,
    mu_earth, dt, flaga, sp, sv)
```

```
Q = 0.01*eye(6);
```

```
R = diag([sp^2 sp^2 sp^2 sv^2 sv^2 sv^2]);
```

```
H = eye(6);
```

```
k1 = f(x, mu_earth);
```

```
k2 = f(x + dt*k1/2, mu_earth);
```

```
k3 = f(x + dt*k2/2, mu_earth);
```

```
k4 = f(x + dt*k3, mu_earth);
```

```
x_apriori = x + dt/6*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4);
```

```
r = x(1:3);
```

```
nr = norm(r);
```

```
r1 = x(1);
```

```
r2 = x(2);
```

```
r3 = x(3);
```

```
F1 = [(3*mu_earth*r1^2)/nr^5 - mu_earth/nr^3, (3*mu_earth*r1*r2)/nr^5,  
      (3*mu_earth*r1*r3)/nr^5;  
      (3*mu_earth*r1*r2)/nr^5, (3*mu_earth*r2^2)/nr^5 -  
      mu_earth/nr^3, (3*mu_earth*r2*r3)/nr^5;  
      (3*mu_earth*r1*r3)/nr^5, (3*mu_earth*r2*r3)/nr^5,  
      (3*mu_earth*r3^2)/nr^5 - mu_earth/nr^3];
```

```
F = [zeros(3,3), eye(3);  
     F1, zeros(3,3)];
```

```
F2 = eye(6) + F*dt;
```

```
P_apriori = F2*P*F2' + Q;
```

```
residual = x_meas - x_apriori;
```

```
S = H*P_apriori*H' + R;
```

```
if flaga == 1
```

```

        K = P_apriori*H'/S;
    else
        K = zeros(6);
    end

    x_aposteriori = x_apriori + K*residual;
    P_aposteriori = (eye(6) - K*H)*P_apriori;

    x_updated = x_aposteriori;
    P_updated = P_aposteriori;

end

function dx = f(x, MG)
    r = x(1:3);
    v = x(4:6);
    r_t = norm(r)^3;
    dx = [v; -MG*r/r_t];
end

```

B.3 J2 perturbation model diagram

FIGURE B.4. Main body of J2 perturbation model Simulink block diagram.

FIGURE B.5. Real satellite position and velocity (GMAT) block diagram.

FIGURE B.6. Measurement device failure block diagram.

B.4 J2 perturbation model function

```
function [x_updated, P_updated] = orbit_kalman(x, P, x_meas,
    mu_earth, dt, flaga, sp, sv, Re, J2)
```

```

Q = 0.01*eye(6);
R = diag([sp^2 sp^2 sp^2 sv^2 sv^2 sv^2]);

H = eye(6);

k1 = forbit(x, mu_earth, Re, J2);
k2 = forbit(x + dt*k1/2, mu_earth, Re, J2);
k3 = forbit(x + dt*k2/2, mu_earth, Re, J2);
k4 = forbit(x + dt*k3, mu_earth, Re, J2);

x_apriori = x + dt/6*(k1+2*k2+2*k3+k4);

r = x(1:3);
nr = norm(r);
r1 = x(1);
r2 = x(2);
r3 = x(3);

F1 = [-mu_earth*(1/nr^3 - (3*r1^2)/nr^5 + (J2*Re^2*(3/nr^5 - (15*
r1^2)/nr^7 - (15*r3^2)/nr^7 + (105*r1^2*r3^2)/nr^9))/2),
mu_earth*((3*r1*r2)/nr^5 + (J2*Re^2*((15*r1*r2)/nr^7 - (105*r1
*r2*r3^2)/nr^9))/2),
mu_earth*((3*r1*r3)/nr^5 + (J2*Re^2*((45*r1*r3)/nr^7 - (105*r1
*r3^3)/nr^9))/2);

```

$$\begin{aligned}
& \mu_{\text{earth}} * ((3 * r1 * r2) / nr^5 + (J2 * Re^2 * ((15 * r1 * r2) / nr^7 - \\
& \quad (105 * r1 * r2 * r3^2) / nr^9)) / 2), \\
& \quad -\mu_{\text{earth}} * (1 / nr^3 - (3 * \\
& \quad r2^2) / nr^5 + (J2 * Re^2 * (3 / nr^5 - (15 * r2^2) / nr^7 - (15 * r3 \\
& \quad ^2) / nr^7 + (105 * r2^2 * r3^2) / nr^9)) / 2), \quad \mu_{\text{earth}} * ((3 * r2 \\
& \quad * r3) / nr^5 + (J2 * Re^2 * ((45 * r2 * r3) / nr^7 - (105 * r2 * r3^3) / \\
& \quad nr^9)) / 2); \\
& \mu_{\text{earth}} * ((3 * r1 * r3) / nr^5 + (J2 * Re^2 * ((45 * r1 * r3) / nr^7 - \\
& \quad (105 * r1 * r3^3) / nr^9)) / 2), \\
& \quad \mu_{\text{earth}} * ((3 * r2 * r3) \\
& \quad / nr^5 + (J2 * Re^2 * ((45 * r2 * r3) / nr^7 - (105 * r2 * r3^3) / nr^9) \\
& \quad) / 2), \quad -\mu_{\text{earth}} * (1 / \\
& \quad nr^3 - (3 * r3^2) / nr^5 + (J2 * Re^2 * (9 / nr^5 - (90 * r3^2) / nr \\
& \quad ^7 + (105 * r3^4) / nr^9)) / 2)];
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
F &= [\mathbf{zeros}(3,3), \mathbf{eye}(3); \\
& \quad F1, \mathbf{zeros}(3,3)];
\end{aligned}$$

$$F2 = \mathbf{eye}(6) + F * dt;$$

$$P_{\text{apriori}} = F2 * P * F2' + Q;$$

$$\text{residual} = x_{\text{meas}} - x_{\text{apriori}};$$

$$S = H * P_{\text{apriori}} * H' + R;$$

```

if flaga == 1
    K = P_apriori*H'/S;
else
    K = zeros(6);
end

x_aposteriori = x_apriori + K*residual;
P_aposteriori = (eye(6) - K*H)*P_apriori;

x_updated = x_aposteriori;
P_updated = P_aposteriori;

end

```

```

function x_dot = forbit(x, mu, Re, J2)
px = x(1);
py = x(2);
pz = x(3);
v = x(4:6);
r = sqrt(px^2 + py^2 + pz^2);
A_J2 = 0.5 * J2 * Re^2;

ax = mu * (-px/r^3 + A_J2 * (15*px*pz^2/r^7 - 3*px/r^5));
ay = mu * (-py/r^3 + A_J2 * (15*py*pz^2/r^7 - 3*py/r^5));
az = mu * (-pz/r^3 + A_J2 * (15*pz*pz^2/r^7 - 9*pz/r^5));

```

```
x_dot = [v; ax; ay; az];
```

```
end
```

Chapter C

Appendix C: MATLAB code

C.1 Central gravity model with no failure

```
 Tp = 1; % sample time
 tsim = 6000; % simulation time, s

 sp = 100/3;
 sv = 2/3;

 [x, y, z, vx, vy, vz] = importfile('MC_Report.txt'); %read
    external data
 xt = [(1:numel(x))' x];
 yt = [(1:numel(y))' y];
 zt = [(1:numel(z))' z];
 vxt = [(1:numel(vx))' vx];
 vyt = [(1:numel(vy))' vy];
 vzt = [(1:numel(vz))' vz];
```

```

seed_noise = [1 2 3 4 5 6]';

% Case 1
Ft1 = 1e20;
Ft2 = 1e20; % no failure
out = sim('Kalman2_NoJ2.slx'); % run simulation
no_samples = size(out.p_est,3);
out.p_est = reshape(out.p_est,3,no_samples)';
out.v_est = reshape(out.v_est,3,no_samples)'; % end of simulation

%%
figure(1)
clf
h1 = plot3(out.p_real(:,1),out.p_real(:,2),out.p_real(:,3));
hold on
h2 = plot3(out.p_est(:,1),out.p_est(:,2),out.p_est(:,3),'—');
axis equal
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure1.eps','epsc');

%%
figure(2)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_real);
hold on

```

```

h2 = plot(out.p_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure2.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(2002)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out.p_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure2002.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(3)
clf
h1 = plot(out.v_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out.v_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')

```

```

saveas(gca, 'figure3.eps', 'epsc');

%%
figure(3003)
clf
h1 = plot(out.v_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out.v_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure3003.eps', 'epsc');

```

```

%%
figure(4)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_est-out.p_real);
hold on
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
%saveas(gca, 'figure4.eps', 'epsc');

```

```

%%
figure(5)
clf

```

```
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-out.  
p_real(end-3000:end,:));
```

```
sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(1,1,:),size(out.P,3),1));
```

```
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(2,2,:),size(out.P,3),1));
```

```
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(3,3,:),size(out.P,3),1));
```

```
hold on
```

```
h2 = plot(3*sx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma
```

```
h3 = plot(-3*sx_est(end-3000:end));
```

```
h4 = plot(3*sy_est(end-500:end));
```

```
h5 = plot(-3*sy_est(end-500:end));
```

```
h6 = plot(3*sz_est(end-500:end));
```

```
h7 = plot(-3*sz_est(end-500:end));
```

```
grid on
```

```
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
```

```
saveas(gca, 'figure5.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(6)
```

```
clf
```

```
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out.v_est(end-3000:end,:)-out.  
v_real(end-3000:end,:));
```

```
grid on,
```

```
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
```

```

saveas(gcf, 'figure6.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(7)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out.v_est(end-3000:end, :) - out.v_real(end-3000:end, :));

svx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(4,1,:), size(out.P,3), 1));
svy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(5,2,:), size(out.P,3), 1));
svz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(6,3,:), size(out.P,3), 1));

hold on

h2 = plot(3*svx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*svx_est(end-3000:end));
h4 = plot(3*svy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*svy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*svz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*svz_est(end-500:end));

grid on

fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gcf, 'figure7.eps', 'epsc');

```

C.2 Central gravity model with failure

```

Tp = 1; % sample time
tsim = 6000; % simulation time, s
sp = 100/3;
sv = 2/3;

[x, y, z, vx, vy, vz] = importfile('MC_Report.txt'); %read
    external data
xt = [(1:numel(x))' x];
yt = [(1:numel(y))' y];
zt = [(1:numel(z))' z];
vxt = [(1:numel(vx))' vx];
vyt = [(1:numel(vy))' vy];
vzt = [(1:numel(vz))' vz];

%Case 1
Ft1 = 3500;
Ft2 = 5500; % failure

out = sim('Kalman2_NoJ2.slx'); % run simulation
no_samples = size(out.p_est,3);
out.p_est = reshape(out.p_est,3,no_samples)';
out.v_est = reshape(out.v_est,3,no_samples)'; % end of simulation

%%
figure(8)
clf

```

```

h1 = plot3(out.p_real(:,1),out.p_real(:,2),out.p_real(:,3));
hold on
h2 = plot3(out.p_est(:,1),out.p_est(:,2),out.p_est(:,3),'—');
axis equal
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure8.eps','epsc');

```

```
%%
```

```

figure(9)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out.p_est,'—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure9.eps','epsc');

```

```
%%
```

```

figure(9009)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out.p_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on

```

```
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gcf, 'figure9009.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(10)
clf
h1 = plot(out.v_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out.v_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gcf, 'figure10.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(100010)
clf
h1 = plot(out.v_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out.v_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gcf, 'figure100010.eps', 'epsc');
```

```

%%
figure(11)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-out.
    p_real(end-3000:end,:));
hold on
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure11.eps', 'epsc');

```

```

%%
figure(12)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-out.
    p_real(end-3000:end,:));

```

```

sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(1,1,:),size(out.P,3),1));
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(2,2,:),size(out.P,3),1));
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(3,3,:),size(out.P,3),1));

```

```

hold on

```

```

h2 = plot(3*sx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma

```

```

h3 = plot(-3*sx_est(end-3000:end));

```

```

h4 = plot(3*sy_est(end-500:end));

```

```

h5 = plot(-3*sy_est(end-500:end));

```

```

h6 = plot(3*sz_est(end-500:end));

```

```

h7 = plot(-3*sz_est(end-500:end));
grid on

fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure12.eps', 'epsc');

%%
figure(120012)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-510:end-400), out.p_est(end-510:end-400, :) -
        out.p_real(end-510:end-400, :));

sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(1,1,:), size(out.P,3),1));
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(2,2,:), size(out.P,3),1));
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(3,3,:), size(out.P,3),1));
hold on

h2 = plot(3*sx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*sx_est(end-3000:end));
h4 = plot(3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*sz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*sz_est(end-500:end));
grid on

fontname('Times_New_Roman')

```

```

axis([5495 5600 -200 200])
saveas(gca, 'figure120012.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(13)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out.v_est(end-3000:end, :) - out.v_real(end-3000:end, :));
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure13.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(130013)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-510:end-400), out.v_est(end-510:end-400, :) - out.v_real(end-510:end-400, :));

grid on
axis([5495 5600 -1 1])
saveas(gca, 'figure130013.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(14)
clf

```

```
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out.v_est(end-3000:end, :) - out.v_real(end-3000:end, :));
```

```
svx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(4,1,:), size(out.P,3), 1));
```

```
svy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(5,2,:), size(out.P,3), 1));
```

```
svz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(6,3,:), size(out.P,3), 1));
```

```
hold on
```

```
h2 = plot(3*svx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma
```

```
h3 = plot(-3*svx_est(end-3000:end));
```

```
h4 = plot(3*svy_est(end-500:end));
```

```
h5 = plot(-3*svy_est(end-500:end));
```

```
h6 = plot(3*svz_est(end-500:end));
```

```
h7 = plot(-3*svz_est(end-500:end));
```

```
grid on
```

```
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
```

```
saveas(gca, 'figure14.eps', 'epsc');
```

C.3 J2 perturbation model with no failure

```
Tp = 1; % sample time
```

```
tsim = 6000; % simulation time, s
```

```
sp = 100/3;
```

```
sv = 2/3;
```

```

[x, y, z, vx, vy, vz] = importfile('MC_Report.txt'); %read
    external data
xt = [(1:numel(x))' x];
yt = [(1:numel(y))' y];
zt = [(1:numel(z))' z];
vxt = [(1:numel(vx))' vx];
vyt = [(1:numel(vy))' vy];
vzt = [(1:numel(vz))' vz];
seed_noise = [1 2 3 4 5 6]';

% Case 1
Ft1 = 1e20;
Ft2 = 1e20; % no failure
out = sim('Kalman2-J2.slx'); % run simulation
no_samples = size(out.p_est,3);
out.p_est = reshape(out.p_est,3,no_samples)';
out.v_est = reshape(out.v_est,3,no_samples)'; % end of simulation

%%
figure(15)
clf
h1 = plot3(out.p_real(:,1),out.p_real(:,2),out.p_real(:,3));
hold on
h2 = plot3(out.p_est(:,1),out.p_est(:,2),out.p_est(:,3),'—');
axis equal

```

```
grid on
fontname( 'Times_New_Roman' )
saveas(gca, 'figure15.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(16)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out.p_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname( 'Times_New_Roman' )
saveas(gca, 'figure16.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(160016)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out.p_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname( 'Times_New_Roman' )
saveas(gca, 'figure160016.eps', 'epsc');
```

```

%%
figure(17)
clf
h1 = plot(out.v_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out.v_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure17.eps', 'epsc');

```

```

%%
figure(170017)
clf
h1 = plot(out.v_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out.v_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure170017.eps', 'epsc');

```

```

%%
figure(18)
clf
h1 = plot(out.p_est-out.p_real);

```

```

hold on

grid on

xlim([0 6000])

fontname('Times_New_Roman')

saveas(gca, 'figure18.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(19)

clf

h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-out.
    p_real(end-3000:end,:));

sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(1,1,:),size(out.P,3),1));
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(2,2,:),size(out.P,3),1));
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(3,3,:),size(out.P,3),1));

hold on

h2 = plot(3*sx_est(end-500:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*sx_est(end-500:end));
h4 = plot(3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*sz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*sz_est(end-500:end));

grid on

fontname('Times_New_Roman')

```

```

saveas(gca, 'figure19.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(20)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out.v_est(end-3000:end, :)-out.v_real(end-3000:end, :));

grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure20.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(21)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out.v_est(end-3000:end, :)-out.v_real(end-3000:end, :));

svx_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(4, 1, :), size(out_J2.P, 3), 1));
svy_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(5, 2, :), size(out_J2.P, 3), 1));
svz_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(6, 3, :), size(out_J2.P, 3), 1));

hold on

h2 = plot(3*svx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*svx_est(end-3000:end));

```

```

h4 = plot(3*svy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*svy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*svz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*svz_est(end-500:end));
hold on

```

```

grid on

```

```

fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure21.eps', 'epsc');

```

C.4 J2 perturbation model with failure

```

Tp = 1; % sample time
tsim = 6000; % simulation time, s

sp = 100/3;
sv = 2/3;

[x, y, z, vx, vy, vz] = importfile('MC_Report.txt'); %wczytaj dane
                z zewnatrz
xt = [(1:numel(x))' x];
yt = [(1:numel(y))' y];
zt = [(1:numel(z))' z];
vxt = [(1:numel(vx))' vx];
vyt = [(1:numel(vy))' vy];
vzt = [(1:numel(vz))' vz];

```

```

% Case 1
Ft1 = 3500;
Ft2 = 5500; % failure

out = sim('Kalman2_J2.slx'); % run simulation
no_samples = size(out.p_est,3);
out_J2 = out;
out_J2.p_est = reshape(out.p_est,3,no_samples)';
out_J2.v_est = reshape(out.v_est,3,no_samples)'; % end of
    simulation

out = sim('Kalman2_NoJ2.slx'); % run simulation
no_samples = size(out.p_est,3);
out.p_est = reshape(out.p_est,3,no_samples)';
out.v_est = reshape(out.v_est,3,no_samples)'; % end of simulation

%%
figure(22)
clf
h1 = plot3(out.p_real(:,1),out.p_real(:,2),out.p_real(:,3));
hold on
h2 = plot3(out.p_est(:,1),out.p_est(:,2),out.p_est(:,3),'—');
axis equal
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')

```

```
saveas(figure(22), 'figure22', 'eps')
saveas(gca, 'figure22.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(23)
clf
h1 = plot(out_J2.p_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out_J2.p_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure23.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(230023)
clf
h1 = plot(out_J2.p_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out_J2.p_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure230023.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```

figure(24)
clf
h1 = plot(out_J2.v_real);
hold on
h2 = plot(out_J2.v_est, '—');
grid on
xlim([0 6000])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure24.eps', 'epsc');

```

```
%%
```

```

figure(240024)
clf
h1 = plot(out_J2.v_real(end-6000:end-5500,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out_J2.v_est(end-6000:end-5500,:), '—');
grid on
xlim([0 500])
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure240024.eps', 'epsc');

```

```
%%
```

```

figure(25)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out_J2.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-
    out_J2.p_real(end-3000:end,:));

```

```

hold on

grid on

fontname( 'Times_New_Roman' )

saveas(gca, 'figure25.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(26)

clf

h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out_J2.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-
        out_J2.p_real(end-3000:end,:));

sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(1,1,:), size(out_J2.P,3),1));
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(2,2,:), size(out_J2.P,3),1));
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(3,3,:), size(out_J2.P,3),1));

hold on

h2 = plot(3*sx_est(end-500:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*sx_est(end-500:end));
h4 = plot(3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*sz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*sz_est(end-500:end));

grid on

fontname( 'Times_New_Roman' )

saveas(gca, 'figure26.eps', 'epsc');

```

```

%%
figure(260026)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-510:end-400),out_J2.p_est(end-510:end-400,:)-out_J2.p_real(end-510:end-400,:));

sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(1,1,:),size(out_J2.P,3),1));
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(2,2,:),size(out_J2.P,3),1));
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(3,3,:),size(out_J2.P,3),1));
hold on

h2 = plot(3*sx_est(end-500:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*sx_est(end-500:end));
h4 = plot(3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*sy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*sz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*sz_est(end-500:end));

grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
axis([5495 5600 -200 200])
saveas(gca, 'figure260026.eps', 'epsc');

%%
figure(27)

```

```

clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out_J2.v_est(end-3000:end,:)-
    out_J2.v_real(end-3000:end,:));
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')

%%

figure(270027)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-505:end-400),out_J2.v_est(end-505:end
    -400,:)-out_J2.v_real(end-505:end-400,:));
grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
axis([5495 5600 -1 1])
saveas(gca, 'figure270027.eps', 'epsc');

%%

figure(28)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out_J2.v_est(end-3000:end,:)-
    out_J2.v_real(end-3000:end,:));

svx_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(4,1,:),size(out_J2.P,3),1));
svy_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(5,2,:),size(out_J2.P,3),1));
svz_est = sqrt(reshape(out_J2.P(6,3,:),size(out_J2.P,3),1));
hold on

```

```

h2 = plot(3*svx_est(end-3000:end)); %sigma
h3 = plot(-3*svx_est(end-3000:end));
h4 = plot(3*svy_est(end-500:end));
h5 = plot(-3*svy_est(end-500:end));
h6 = plot(3*svz_est(end-500:end));
h7 = plot(-3*svz_est(end-500:end));

grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')

%%

figure(29)
clf
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end),out.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-out.p_real(end-3000:end,:));
hold on
h2 = plot(out_J2.tout(end-3000:end),out_J2.p_est(end-3000:end,:)-out_J2.p_real(end-3000:end,:), '—');

sx_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(1,1,:),size(out.P,3),1));
sy_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(2,2,:),size(out.P,3),1));
sz_est = sqrt(reshape(out.P(3,3,:),size(out.P,3),1));

grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')

```

```
saveas(gca, 'figure29.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(30)
```

```
clf
```

```
h1 = plot(out.tout(end-3000:end), out.v_est(end-3000:end, :) - out.v_real(end-3000:end, :));
```

```
hold on
```

```
h2 = plot(out_J2.tout(end-3000:end), out_J2.v_est(end-3000:end, :) - out_J2.v_real(end-3000:end, :), '—');
```

```
grid on
```

```
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
```

```
saveas(gca, 'figure30.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(31)
```

```
clf
```

```
h1 = plot(out_J2.tout(end-3000:end), out_J2.noise(end-3000:end, 1:3));
```

```
grid on
```

```
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
```

```
saveas(gca, 'figure31.eps', 'epsc');
```

```
%%
```

```
figure(32)
clf
h1 = plot(out_J2.tout(end-3000:end),out_J2.noise(end-3000:end,4:6)
);

grid on
fontname('Times_New_Roman')
saveas(gca, 'figure32.eps', 'epsc');
```